

Customer satisfaction towards Cups and Thoughts Coffee marketing strategies in Pila, Laguna, Philippines

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Abstract

Today, coffee is one of the most popular beverages for most people, and among the best ways to get a nice serving of it is through purchasing it in a coffee shop. Yet, due to the pandemic, these local businesses have suffered a huge hit in their profit and operating budgets. So, as a response to this problem, the researchers have thought of ways on how to attract and retain consumers, and that is to maximize the satisfaction that a shop could give to its customers. To find the best way to maximize customer satisfaction, the researchers used the quantitative correlational research to find out if there is a relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies, Then, the research focused on a local coffee shop named Cups and Thoughts Coffee, which is in Pila, Laguna to gather the data needed. The researchers then interviewed the owner to gather information about the shop, how they operate and the marketing strategies that they use. With the gathered data, the researchers formulated a survey questionnaire that was given to the customers of the shop. After analyzing the gathered data, the results show that the customers of Cups and Thoughts Coffee has used and experienced their marketing strategies, and because of that, they are also satisfied with the shop's products and services, and due to that, the researchers have found out that there is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies. From the results of the research, it can be interpreted that good marketing strategies will greatly satisfy the customers, which will then be converted to better profitability of the business.

Keywords: *Customer satisfaction; coffee; marketing strategies; products; services.*

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Introduction

The Cups and Thoughts Coffee is a newly opened coffee shop in Pila, Laguna, Philippines. The coffee shop started its operation last December 19, 2020. The theme of the coffee shop is to incorporate the vision and what the brand stands for, Cups and Thoughts will be branded as “*sun shines and memories in a cup of coffee.*” To achieve this objective, we would like to contrast the bright morning colors similar to morning sky to the solid concrete finish to be able to highlight the aesthetic simplicity of the cafe. The shop prioritize to be budget friendly and aesthetically eye pleasing shop at the same time with professionally trained staff.

Coffee is a popular beverage enjoyed in many different ways worldwide. Many deem drinking coffee the best way to start the day, soothe a dismal mood, and energize a tired body. Hence, consumers get a cup of quality coffee by visiting local coffee shops. These small businesses may be unfamiliar at first, and the quality of their products and services is unknown, but there are ways to find good local coffee shops. The process, however, can be compared to finding a diamond in the rough.

According to Tumanan and Lansangan (2012), coffee consumption is viewed by others as an experience, instead of it being just a product to be consumed. It is observed when local coffee shops provide their customers with unique interior design and calming ambiance. Additionally, the self-developed recipes of coffee shop owners represent their ideology and vision, which contribute to customers' overall experience as they drink them.

In the same study, it was found that one of the main problems coffee shop owners struggle with is their lack of utilization in marketing strategies to attract more customers. Marketing strategies are regarded with the same level of importance as putting up a business itself and planning and implementing them influence their profitability.

One of the factors that needs to be considered in creating a business, especially a local coffee shop, is to achieve customer satisfaction. According to Cengiz (2010), customer satisfaction may be felt in several circumstances and can be linked to both goods and services. It is a very subjective assessment that is often swayed by clients' expectations. A customer's happiness is influenced by both the experience achieved with the brand and their respective outcomes. Client retention has gotten a lot of attention in the literature, according to Danesh et al. (2012), because of its importance in determining an organization's financial performance. In today's market, competitiveness is a must if the establishment wishes to satisfy and obtain consumer loyalty. The better customer satisfaction rate they receive, the higher the profitability. It can be concluded that customer satisfaction generates its own publicity through continuous paid and unpaid advertisements they acquire from those availing the products and services.

Delivering an effective marketing strategy has to have a great extent of factors to be considered in order to attain individual confidence. As the target audience constantly expands, business owners plan marketing strategies that cater to their growing needs. They create an environment where people would want to keep coming back because of their accommodating and comfortable ambiance. The technological advancements helped create a safe, cozy workspace for adults, and an enjoyable place to unwind and chat for the teenagers. It pushed companies to develop further and provide for reliable Internet connection, so that consumers' demands are met while they enjoy their innovative beverage and snack creations.

The main goal of this quantitative correlational study is to figure out how consumer satisfaction and marketing strategies are related to each other. To test this, the researchers chose to conduct this study in one of the coffee shops located in Pila, Laguna, the Cups and Thoughts Coffee. The researchers deemed this shop as a suitable candidate to be the subject of this research since it was opened last December 2020, which makes this shop have over a year of operating experience.

The results of this research can help Cups and Thoughts Coffee and other local coffee shops create their own or improve their marketing strategies, so that they can attract more customers. This academic paper can serve as reference on customer satisfaction and marketing strategy since it also explores and provides the needed data about it and the elements involved.

Related Literature

Customer Satisfaction

The goal of this study is to determine the characteristics or aspects that have a significant influence on consumer satisfaction in this business, particularly within Pakistan. It is said to be critical to achieving customer happiness. The level of client happiness is determined by the organization's brand qualities. Customer satisfaction, according to Khan and Afsheen (2012), is described as satisfying customers' expectations in terms of satisfaction-related factors (Malik & Ghaffor, 2012). Customer satisfaction with a company's products and services has long been acknowledged as a strategic aspect in attaining a competitive edge. Client contentment is the way that leads to undefined long-term customer retention in the context of marketing since dissatisfied consumers usually transfer.

Academics and practitioners have paid more attention to store atmospheres, which play an essential role in influencing customer satisfaction. The five primary human senses such as hearing, smell, sight, taste, and touch can all be used to record atmospherics. Bitner (1992) has mentioned ambient conditions, spatial arrangement and functionality, as well as signs, symbols, and artifacts as a metric for atmospherics, or the Servicescape, as she named it.

Items like attractive employees, a sufficient number of employees, and well-presented staff are used as indicators of employee quality. The facility aesthetics variable will focus solely on internal design and decoration, whereas the ambiance variable will include background music, odors in the dining area, lighting, and temperature.

Perceived value is another thing that has an impact on customer behavior. Customers are getting increasingly concerned about the significance of value. By examining the hotel context, Walls (2012) further said that customers' perceptions of the value of hotel services are influenced by their experiences with hotels. Value is characterized as a customer's total assessment of the service's net worth based on the advantages sought and the costs associated with acquiring and using the services.

Customer satisfaction can lead to repurchases and positive word-of-mouth which are the future behavioral intentions, according to Ryu and Han (2011). Customer loyalty, on the other hand, is influenced by customer satisfaction and it has a lot of positive effects on a company. Customers will continue doing business with a company once they have placed their trust in it and are assured that the company will provide their wants and needs. It should be the organization's top concern because customers drive business. Customer satisfaction statistics may help one's company determine what internal procedures, products, and services are performing well, as well as what should be improved or replaced totally.

Marketing Strategies

Any marketing strategy is critical since it determines how the company will operate. Smell, touch, taste, sight, and sound are the five senses we have, but will it have an influence if these senses are the primary focus of marketing strategies, allowing the senses to aid in business growth? This type of marketing strategy is now one of the greatest options since it allows people to see and feel the product that has been offered to them.

Brand image is critical for any products and services since it acts as a façade for any product. When you hear a brand, you automatically assume something similar, but having a brand image is essential because there are only two types of images: bad and good. One of the finest examples is the Starbucks coffee shop; when you hear the name Starbucks, you automatically think of wonderful coffee and a high-end coffee shop, which is a fantastic brand image.

Considering coffee beans are particularly fragrant, the coffee shop and the sensory marketing strategy are a great match. Because of the scent or aroma, it can already encourage consumers to buy coffee. Aroma, presentation, and product flavor are all important factors in any company, but they are more important in coffee shops because most of these establishments only provide coffee and a few nibbles. Because customers' behavior and decision-making processes are critical aspects (Hultén et al., 2009), the customer's consumption process should be evaluated using human senses. Human senses can affect consumer decisions due to impulses and quick decision-making. People may be readily convinced if the five senses are incorporated in their decision making, since they can already see, smell, and taste the goods, as Hultén et al. (2009) stated, which is why coffee shops should already use this type of strategy to increase sales. Using the internet and online advertising is one of the most efficient marketing tactics right now, but in order to have a good online campaign, they must have excellent product visualization so that customers can see what they can get.

More clients will be drawn to the company if all five senses are included in the marketing approach (Lindstrom, 2005). Because of the influence of olfactory, gustative, tactical, visual, and sonorous, the researcher had the concept that the five senses could be a marketing strategy in this study, and as a consumer, you would have a fantastic expression about that brand if your five senses can be fulfilled by that product. Elder et al. (2011) explained that there is a need to recognize that services and goods are sensuous in nature, and that a consumer must be able to experience all five senses: sight, taste, touch, sound, and smell. This study would be useful for the current research because it already addresses the sensory marketing strategy despite it focusing on multinational fast-food chains. This research will also help ascertain that marketing methods have an impact on customer satisfaction.

The first five years of operation are the most critical times for businesses. This is due to the fact that business owners have yet to experience the essential sustenance that they need to survive the trials of the industry (He et al., 2018). The largest coffee shop in the world, Starbucks, whose first store opened in 1971 had also experienced store closures throughout its company history. According to Knoema (2021), Starbucks closed 443 stores, 240 stores in 2009, 42 in 2010, and 161 in 2011. It was not even in the five-year period when Starbucks had its first store closure, meaning that a business' key to success is through marketing strategies such as personal branding, persistence, experience, and cooperation (Resnick et al., 2016). Goldsmith's 8 Ps of the marketing mix is the system used in this study because it has all the components both included in McCarthy's (1960) traditional 4 Ps and Booms and Bitner's (1981) 7 Ps.

Researchers found that the 8 Ps of the marketing mix is useful for this study as it provides a wide range of recommendations that owners of coffee shops can utilize in order to keep their operations running smoothly during its first five years (Adeleke, 2020). This marketing mix concept focuses on the holistic marketing approach with the addition of people, processes, programs, and performance. Social media adoption and improving frontline engagement are the focal point of discerning whether the marketing strategies used by Coffee Shop X helps in achieving customer satisfaction in this study. Adeleke (2020) found that small businesses play an important part in the economy of the United States. It was determined due to the fact that they are often independent, and they only require less than 500 personnel to keep operating.

Coffee shops rely a lot on social media, especially during these difficult times. Communication tools such as verbal evidence passed through different individuals or groups relay figures and details to help the brand build its reputation (Huete-Alcocer, 2017). The 8 Ps will justify whether a marketing strategy is effective in ensuring that a business attains the satisfaction of the public and sustains their services even after five years in the industry. The program, as well as the performance aspects, explained in the 8 Ps of the marketing mix, is necessary for entrepreneurs to know as it can improve the web-based distinction of their company could also entail improved exposure on search engines, and is therefore significant in sustaining a company.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine customer satisfaction toward the marketing strategies of Cups and Thoughts Coffee in Pila, Laguna.

1. What are the views of the respondents toward the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee?
 - 1.1. Promotion
 - 1.2. Place
 - 1.3. Product
 - 1.4. Performance
 - 1.5. Price

2. What is the level of satisfaction of the customers of Cups and Thoughts Coffee according to their marketing strategies?
3. Is there a relationship between marketing strategies and customer satisfaction?

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies.

Theoretical Framework

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is defined by Janahi and Al Mubarak (2017) as the measurement of a customer's happiness with an organization's goods, services, or other selling procedures, including customer service. On the other hand, Hassan and Shamsudin (2019) stated that customer satisfaction is determined by the satisfaction customers get when the company provides items or services that are equal to their aspirations. As shown in a study, customer satisfaction is influenced by the consumer's capacity to pay and get when the company provides items or services that meet their demands. Customer satisfaction, according to Oliver (1981), is the personification of psychological fulfillment of customers, and consumer experience is the fundamental purpose of products or services. Crompton and MacKay (1989) also defines customer satisfaction as the perspective of customers, and this perception is established when customers' expectations of products or services are met. Customer happiness is the overall outcome of this comparison.

Cardozo's (1965) definition of customer satisfaction is slightly different from that of Janahi and Al Mubarak (2017). He said that customer satisfaction is the most important element influencing repeat purchases. Customer satisfaction, he believes, is the most significant factor influencing customers to keep coming back. He also stated that customer contentment is mostly driven by two factors: the buyers' desires for products and services and the actual items or services they receive. The definition given by Janahi and Al Mubarak (2017) is the most applicable to the study's goals and objectives, which are to determine the relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies. Although Cardozo (1965) stated that consumer expectations of the product influence customer experience, this is irrelevant because this study only examines data that can be assessed.

Marketing Strategy

Coffee shops must have a marketing strategy in order to survive. According to Nguyen et al. (2015), good marketing techniques are critical to the survival of coffee businesses. The 8 Ps of marketing mix theory were created by Goldsmith (1999). Personalization of products can set a brand differently. To turn marketing theory and practice into a personalized era, Goldsmith (1999) underlined the necessity of the 8 Ps of the marketing mix. The main point for the 8 Ps' significance was that managers needed to develop marketing strategies that included personalization in addition to McCarthy's (1960) standard 4Ps (product, price, promotion, location), Booms and Bitner's (1981).

The eighth P in the 7Ps (adding personnel, physical evidence, and procedure) is to create an inventive marketing mix. The traditional marketing mix aspects of product, price, venue, and promotion, as per Mukherjee and Shivani (2016), were insufficient in attaining marketing goals in services. Pomeroy (2017) also proposed that smaller businesses that employ the marketing mix could be beneficial from reconfiguring the old 4Ps to reflect a developing, sustainable society.

This study adopted Goldsmith's (1999) 8 Ps marketing mix theory to assess the success of two marketing strategies: social media adoption and improving frontline engagement. Oncioiu et al. (2020) asserted that a company's online reputation improves its search engine exposure. Kujur and Singh (2017) suggested that business owners create a strategy for their preferred social media platform and online social media presence.

Social media adoption and improving frontline engagement are the theories used in this study alongside/considering the 8 Ps marketing mix of Goldsmith (1999). These theories will aid the researchers in interpreting the study's outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

The framework shows the 8 Ps of the marketing mix that serve as bases in determining customer satisfaction towards Cups and Thoughts Coffee's marketing strategies. The conceptual framework presents the dependent variable which is customer satisfaction. The independent variables which are marketing strategies and is further specified as the 8 Ps or as follows: promotion, product, place, price, people, physical evidence, process, and performance.

Figure 1. 8 Ps Marketing Strategies – Customer Satisfaction

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative correlational design is used in this research. It is a research design that investigates the relationship between two or more variables, which is suitable to be used in this study, as it is aimed to determine if there is a relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the customers of Cups and Thoughts Coffee in Pila, Laguna. To determine the sample of respondents required for this study, the researchers used simple random sampling where in a given population, every individual has an equal probability of being chosen. In this research, the regular customers who are within the age range of eighteen (18) up to sixty (60) were randomly selected to be the respondents and were asked for consent and permission to answer the questionnaire. People under the age of eighteen (18) and those beyond the age of sixty (60) were excluded from the survey. We excluded those under the age of 18 because having minors as respondents entail a different set of procedures, while those over 60 were not encouraged since this research was conducted during a pandemic. Both minors and senior citizens are discouraged from going to public places such as malls and coffee shops. The respondents include both first timers and frequent customers.

Instruments

The researchers designed a questionnaire as the instrument for this study. The survey questions are aimed to know the relationship between customer satisfaction and Cups and Thoughts Coffee shop marketing strategies. A questionnaire is a type of research tool that consists of a series of questions designed to gather information from respondents. A questionnaire has the advantage of being able to engage a large number of individuals, provide measurable responses, and be effectively analyzed. It can lessen the time consuming unlike in an interview or observation.

The contents of the questionnaire are a mix of dichotomous and scaling questions. It is divided into three sections: the first is to determine the demographics of the respondents, the second seeks to determine whether the shop has a different marketing mix such as the 8 Ps, and the third seeks to determine the level of customer satisfaction. In order to construct a better question, the researcher must first gain a thorough understanding of the target population's preferences, age, and other factors. The researchers must be able to provide explanation on the nature of the questions as well as how the results will be thoroughly investigated. The survey questionnaire was also put under pilot testing to ensure that each question was reliable. The Cronbach Alpha value for the reliability tests was 0.93.

Data Gathering Procedure

During the study's data gathering through survey questionnaire, the researchers created a survey questionnaire that focuses on Cups and Thoughts Coffee's marketing strategies and the customers' satisfaction toward it. The researchers asked permission to conduct the survey from the coffee shop owner. Once the researchers were given permission, they sent the survey questionnaires through Google Form and asked the coffee shop owner and staff to disseminate it to their clients in order to attain the response and feedback of the respondents. After the survey was administered, the researchers analyzed the results of the survey. The output made by the researchers were then reviewed by a statistician in order to ensure the right interpretation of the results and is then displayed through tables.

The data gathered from the surveys were the information used in identifying the relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies. The researchers employed the statistical treatment Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson's r) to assess the linear relationship between marketing strategies and customer satisfaction. The statistical method is used to answer the research question. The researchers also used mean and standard deviation to verbally interpret the results of the survey. In order to scale in which respondents define their level of agreement to a statement, a Likert scale was provided.

Results and Discussion

Research Question No. 1: *What are the views of the respondents toward the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee?*

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Views on the Marketing Mix Used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee in Terms of Promotion

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	I have received fliers that contain information about this shop and what they offer.	4.27	0.65	Strongly Agree
2.	I have encountered a social media post about this coffee shop and saw their products and special offers on their page.	4.49	0.63	Strongly Agree
3.	I have heard about this shop's products and special offers in public places (e.g., malls, supermarkets).	4.07	0.63	Agree
4.	A person I know recommended this shop to me.	4.47	0.63	Strongly Agree
TOTAL		4.33	0.66	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Strongly Agree); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Agree); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Disagree); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Strongly Disagree).

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' views on the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee when planning and formulating their marketing strategies in terms of promotion. As presented, all of the statements about promotion have the computed mean of 4.33 and the computed standard deviation is 0.66. The computed mean of 4.33 has a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. This means that the customers fully agree that there is the presence of promotional marketing strategies of the coffee shop and experience it through fliers, social media posts, and recommendations from friends and relatives, and only the promotional marketing strategies of the coffee shop in public places are lacking when compared to their other strategies.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Views on the Marketing Mix Used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee in Terms of Place

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	The location of the place can be easily found because of the look of the store from outside.	4.45	0.63	Strongly Agree
2.	The shop is near other landmarks that can be used to find it.	4.49	0.60	Strongly Agree
3.	I can use navigation apps (ex. Google Maps) to locate this coffee shop.	4.43	0.56	Strongly Agree
4.	There are signages and posters that can be found in the area that tells me the direction where the shop can be located.	4.22	0.53	Strongly Agree
TOTAL		4.40	0.59	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Strongly Agree); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Agree); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Disagree); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Strongly Disagree).

Table 2.2 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' views on the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee when planning and formulating their marketing strategies in terms of place. As presented, the mean of all statements combined were totaled up to 4.4, while the standard deviation has 0.59 respectively. The verbal interpretation for all the statements resulted in Strongly Agree.

This shows that most of the respondents found the location of the Cups and Thoughts Coffee accessible and convenient because of the landmarks near the area, its availability in navigation applications, and the signages and posters directing the customers straight to the address of the establishment.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Views on the Marketing Mix Used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee in terms of Product

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	The shop offers many beverage products in their menu.	4.49	0.50	Strongly Agree
2.	The shop offers different types and flavors of beverages to their menu that are unique aside from the common products available on every coffee shop.	4.33	0.58	Strongly Agree
3.	The shop offers various brews in their menu.	4.45	0.63	Strongly Agree
4.	The shop uses different types of coffee beans that makes their brews and other coffee-based products unique from other shops.	4.40	0.56	Strongly Agree
5.	The shop offers a variety of pastries and dishes that can be enjoyed with coffee and other beverages.	4.49	0.63	Strongly Agree
6.	The shop makes sure that their treats and dishes offered are made using their own recipe which makes them unique from other shops.	4.45	0.57	Strongly Agree
TOTAL		4.44	0.58	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Strongly Agree); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Agree); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Disagree); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Strongly Disagree).

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' views about the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee when planning and formulating their marketing strategies in terms of product. As shown in the table, the computed mean of 4.44 has a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. The result shows that the majority of the respondents strongly agree to all the statements that indicate that the Cups and Thoughts Coffee offer a variety of products that makes it stand out among other coffee shops found on the market, as well as pastries and treats that satisfy the customers alongside their beverage orders. It also proves the exceptional and innovative products of the said coffee shop that determine their customer's satisfaction.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Views on the Marketing Mix Used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee in terms of Performance

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	The staff consistently serves their products in their best quality.	4.58	0.50	Strongly Agree
2.	The staff can solve any problems that I might have during my stay in their shop.	4.51	0.57	Strongly Agree
3.	The baristas are very knowledgeable about the products of the shop, and they can give recommendations according to my cravings.	4.53	0.57	Strongly Agree
4.	The shop provides their products in the exact way that they described or pictured it in their menu and promotions.	4.47	0.54	Strongly Agree
TOTAL		4.52	0.54	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Strongly Agree); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Agree); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Disagree); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Strongly Disagree).

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' views on the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee when planning and formulating their marketing strategies in terms of performance. As presented, the computed mean of all statements has a total of 4.52 and the computed standard deviation of 0.54. The computed mean of 4.52 has a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. The results show that Cups and Thoughts Coffee has been consistent with their performance toward their service to customers, ensuring that the staff are well trained and prepared for any challenges and problems given throughout the day and focused on providing only the best quality products to their customers for their satisfaction.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Views on the Marketing Mix Used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee in terms of Price

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	The prices of their products are affordable for me so I can buy it and not have any issues with my money.	4.42	0.60	Strongly Agree
2.	The quality of the products that they offer deserves the price it has.	4.55	0.60	Strongly Agree
3.	The price of their products does not make me rethink if I will go back again to dine.	4.50	0.64	Strongly Agree
4.	The price of their products is reasonable, and it also shows on how they present and pack it.	4.52	0.54	Strongly Agree
TOTAL		4.49	0.59	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Strongly Agree); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Agree); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Disagree); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Strongly Disagree).

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' views on the marketing mix used by Cusp and Thoughts Coffee when planning and formulating their marketing strategies in terms of price. As presented, the computed mean of all the statements has a mean of 4.49 and a standard deviation of 0.59, which has a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. The results show that the customers strongly agree that the coffee shop has carefully thought of their products' pricing. The prices of the products are affordable or budget-friendly, and suitable for the quality of the product.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of the Summary of the Respondents' Views on the Marketing Mix Used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Promotion	4.33	0.66	Strongly Agree
Place	4.40	0.59	Strongly Agree
Product	4.44	0.58	Strongly Agree
Performance	4.52	0.54	Strongly Agree
Price	4.49	0.59	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.44	0.59	Strongly Agree

Table 6 illustrates the descriptive statistics of all of the respondents' views on the marketing mix used by Cups and Thoughts Coffee when planning and formulating their marketing strategies. As the table shows, the average mean has the verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. This shows that the customers strongly agree that the shop has marketing strategies that fit the 5Ps marketing mix and they are experiencing each of the factors through the advertisement practices of the shop, its physical aspects and architectural design, the process of ordering, consuming, and paying of the products, and the hospitality, professionalism, and friendliness of the staff who manage the coffee shop.

Research Question No. 2: What is the level of satisfaction of the customers of Cups and Thoughts Coffee according to their marketing strategies?

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Cups and Thoughts Coffee According to their Marketing Strategy

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	The quality of the coffee brews that this shop offers	4.55	0.57	Very Satisfied
2.	The quality of other beverage products that this shop offers	4.56	0.54	Very Satisfied
3.	The quality of the treats and other dishes that this shop offers	4.64	0.56	Very Satisfied
4.	The number of products that they offer in their menu	4.52	0.54	Very Satisfied
5.	The variety of the products in their menu	4.47	0.64	Very Satisfied
6.	The ease of locating the store	4.31	0.58	Very Satisfied
7.	The special promos this shop gives (e.g., discounts, new brews, coupons)	4.23	0.67	Very Satisfied
8.	The advertisements and the public image of the brand	4.36	0.62	Very Satisfied
9.	The external appearance of the store	4.46	0.54	Very Satisfied
10.	The interior design of the store	4.48	0.58	Very Satisfied
11.	The quality of service that the shop gives	4.60	0.53	Very Satisfied
12.	The professionalism of the staff during working hours	4.47	0.52	Very Satisfied
13.	The process of ordering and paying for the store	4.55	0.54	Very Satisfied
14.	The affordability of each product	4.58	0.57	Very Satisfied
15.	Overall satisfaction about the store	4.60	0.53	Very Satisfied
	TOTAL	4.50	0.59	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 = 5 (Very Satisfied); 3.41-4.20 = 4 (Satisfied); 2.61-3.40 = 3 (Neutral); 1.81-2.60 = 2 (Unsatisfied); and 1.00-1.80 = 1 (Very Unsatisfied).

Table 7 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' level of satisfaction of Cups and Thoughts Coffee according to their marketing strategies. As presented in the data, the computed mean of 4.5 has a verbal interpretation of Very Satisfied. The results show that the customers are very satisfied with how Cups and Thoughts Coffee operates its business. They are pleased with how the service is delivered, the quality and price of the products, the image of the shop and its products, whether it is physically or in advertisements, the process of ordering, staying inside, and paying for the products that they bought, and the promos, discounts, and special events the shop offers during special occasions or as a reward for their loyalty to the store.

Research Question No. 4: Is there a significant relationship between marketing strategies and customer satisfaction?

A Pearson R correlation coefficient was computed to assess the linear relationship between marketing strategies and customer satisfaction. There was a high positive correlation between the two variables, $r(53) = 0.756$, $p = 0.000$. This means that there is a significant relationship between marketing strategies and customer satisfaction.

Table 8. Pearson R Correlation Analysis between Marketing Strategies and Customer Satisfaction

		Factors	Satisfaction Level
Factors	Pearson Correlation	1	.756**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	55	55
Satisfaction Level	Pearson Correlation	.756**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	55	55

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study aims to know the customer satisfaction toward Cups and Thoughts Coffee marketing strategies in Pila, Laguna, Philippines. The majority of the customers in Cups and Thoughts Coffee has teenagers and students. The researchers have concluded that the marketing mix is one of the important factors needed to be considered when formulating marketing strategies. Cups and Thoughts Coffee is very effective with their marketing strategies, as most of their clients were satisfied with their services. Results discovered that there is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and marketing strategies.

For Cups and Thoughts Coffee and other coffee shop owners, the researchers recommend focusing on developing marketing strategies that will appeal to teenagers and students, since this group comprises the most number in the demographic profile of the customers. The Cups and Thoughts Coffee must use and benefit from the internet and various social media platforms to promote their shop so that a larger audience is aware of its existence. They can also hire social media influencers or managers to help them, promoting their shop.

Although the current customers are already satisfied with the food that Cups and Thoughts Coffee are serving, the management must also try to add and formulate new products that the customer may try so that they will have a large variety of choices. For the Performance of the servers, albeit they are knowledgeable already, the management and owner must always train the staff and send them to a seminar where they can learn more and improve more.

The result of this research interprets that the customers of Cups and Thoughts Coffee strongly agree that the shop has employed marketing strategies that correspond with the 8 Ps, which resulted in the customer satisfaction rating of Very Satisfied. It is recommended to maintain this quality of marketing strategies, so that regular customers will always be satisfied and experience the best service the shop has to offer and constantly attract new customers. The promotion and place factors have the lowest scores compared with the other factors of the 8 Ps marketing strategy. These two factors must be given additional attention when planning and creating marketing strategic plans, since these two factors will be the basis of a customer’s first impression of the shop.

The result of this research proves that having effective marketing strategies correlates to a customer’s satisfaction. In order to formulate and plan good marketing strategies, it is recommended that the shop owner must know and cater toward the needs and wants of their customers, display a good impression and identity of the business, whether it is physically or in the social media, and lastly, offer the best products and services the shop has to offer.

Widening the scope of the participants of this study will bring more varied participant inputs that can be helpful in determining the deeper relationship of marketing strategies and customer satisfaction. The researchers suggest that instead of focusing on one shop, conducting a survey to multiple shops, and comparing the ideas and experiences of the customers can bring another set of perspectives and results.

Introducing new variables, like customer loyalty, to be researched will further explain a customer's way of thinking when it comes to consuming products. Applying a qualitative approach will also be beneficial to further explain the psyche of a consumer. Using open-ended questions and interviews will allow the customers to talk about their views and perspectives more freely as they purchase and consume products or services. Onsite observations will also allow future researchers to observe the interactions between the coffee shop and the customers up close.

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